

- BirdLife International: experience in assessing ecosystem services, particularly regarding the TESSA project
- Society for Ecological Restoration (SER): experience in biodiversity and ecological restoration
- Natural Capital Coalition: experience in Natural Capital Knowledge
- IALE: experience in Landscape Ecology.
- IPBES experience in Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
- ESPON EGTC: experience in Spatial Planning
- IFLA Europe: experience in Landscape Planning
- ESP: experience in ecosystem services for conservation and sustainable development
- INTA: experience in Spatial Planning and Territorial Development
- AESOP: experience in Spatial Planning and Urban Development
- ECTP-CEU: experience in Spatial Planning and Urban Development

Fwd: Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practices

 De Nuno Miguel dos Santos David <nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>
Para Isabel Loupa Ramos <isabel.ramos@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>, Jorge Manuel Lopes Baptista e Silva <jbsilva@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>, Lina Maria Hoyos Rojas <lina.maria@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>
Data 2023-05-25 12:03

 Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practice_2.eml (~6 KB)
 Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practice_4.eml (~6 KB)
 Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practice_6.eml (~6 KB)
 Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practice_8.eml (~6 KB)
 Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practice_9.eml (~6 KB)
 Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practice_10.eml (~6 KB)
 Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practice_11.eml (~6 KB)

Bom dia,
Já enviei os e-mails às entidades, personalizando sempre que possível. Seguem para vosso conhecimento (em anexo a este e-mail).
Entre os que nós reunimos e os contributos de Trento, foram 11 entidades.
Não enviei para o ISOCARP porque não encontrei um e-mail, apenas um formulário de contacto. Achar que é de enviar por aí?

Abc,
Nuno.

Assunto Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practices
De Nuno Miguel dos Santos David <nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>
Para <stefano.barchiesi@birdlife.org>
Data 2023-05-25 11:50

Dear Stefano Barchiesi,

Due to the experience of BirdLife International in assessing ecosystem services, particularly regarding TESSA, we are contacting you in the context of the [Horizon 2030 project 'BioValue'](#). This project aims to leverage transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of the EU's strategic actions.

We want to benefit from your expert knowledge and practical experience by collecting information about best practices regarding instruments/projects to value biodiversity in the context of spatial planning.

We kindly request your collaboration to halt biodiversity loss. If halting biodiversity loss aligns with your ambitions, please complete the questionnaire by clicking the link below until June 15. It will take you around 5 minutes: <https://forms.gle/2vyZvus7ar3xQcJm8>

Best regards,

--
Nuno David
(PhD candidate in Territorial Engineering)
CiTUA - Center for Innovation in Territory, Urbanism, and Architecture
University of Lisbon/Instituto Superior Técnico/Department of Civil Engineering, Architecture and Geosources
nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Assunto Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practices
De Nuno Miguel dos Santos David <nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>
Para <info@ser.org>
Data 2023-05-25 11:44

Dear All,

Due to the experience of SER in biodiversity and ecological restoration, we are contacting you in the context of the [Horizon 2030 project 'BioValue'](#). This project aims to leverage transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of the EU's strategic actions.

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Best regards,

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University of Lisbon/Instituto Superior Técnico/Department of Civil Engineering, Architecture and Georesources
nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Assunto Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practices
De Nuno Miguel dos Santos David <nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>
Para <info@capitalscoalition.org>
Data 2023-05-25 11:42

Dear All,

Due to the experience of NCC in Natural Capital knowledge, we are contacting you in the context of the [Horizon 2030 project 'BioValue'](#). This project aims to leverage transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of the EU's strategic actions.

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Best regards,

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nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Assunto Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practices
De Nuno Miguel dos Santos David <nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>
Para <info@landscape-ecology.org>
Data 2023-05-25 11:39

Dear Bastian Steinhoff-Knopp,

Due to the experience of IALE in Landscape Ecology, we are contacting you in the context of the [Horizon 2030 project 'BioValue'](#). This project aims to leverage transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of the EU's strategic actions.

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nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Assunto Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practices
De Nuno Miguel dos Santos David <nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>
Para <secretariat@ipbes.net>
Data 2023-05-25 11:32

Dear All,

Due to the experience of IPBES in Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, we are contacting you in the context of the [Horizon 2030 project 'BioValue'](#). This project aims to leverage transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of the EU's strategic actions.

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Assunto Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practices

De Nuno Miguel dos Santos David <nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>

Para <wiktor.szydarowski@espon.eu>

Cc <info@espon.eu>

Data 2023-05-25 11:29

Dear Wiktor Szydarowski,

Due to the experience of ESPON EGTC in Spatial Planning, we are contacting you in the context of the [Horizon 2030 project 'BioValue'](#). This project aims to leverage transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of the EU's strategic actions.

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Assunto Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practices

De Nuno Miguel dos Santos David <nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>

Para <secretariat@iflaeuropa.eu>

Data 2023-05-25 11:23

Dear All,

Due to the experience of IFLA Europe in Landscape Planning, we are contacting you in the context of the [Horizon 2030 project 'BioValue'](#). This project aims to leverage transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of the EU's strategic actions.

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nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Assunto Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practices

De Nuno Miguel dos Santos David <nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>

Para <info@es-partnership.org>

Data 2023-05-25 11:20

Dear All,

Due to the experience of ESP in ecosystem services for conservation and sustainable development, we are contacting you in the context of the [Horizon 2030](#)

[project 'BioValue'](#). This project aims to leverage transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of the EU's strategic actions.

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nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

Assunto Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practices
De Nuno Miguel dos Santos David <nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>
Para <contact@inta-aivn.org>
Data 2023-05-25 11:13

Dear All,

Due to the experience of INTA in Spatial Planning and Territorial Development, we are contacting you in the context of the [Horizon 2030 project 'BioValue'](#). This project aims to leverage transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of the EU's strategic actions.

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Assunto Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practices
De Nuno Miguel dos Santos David <nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>
Para <secretariat@aesop-planning.eu>
Data 2023-05-25 11:10

Dear All,

Due to the experience of AESOP in Spatial Planning and Urban Development, we are contacting you in the context of the [Horizon 2030 project 'BioValue'](#). This project aims to leverage transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of the EU's strategic actions.

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Assunto Horizon 2030 project 'Biovalue' - Questionnaire of Best practices
De Nuno Miguel dos Santos David <nuno.david@tecnico.ulisboa.pt>
Para <secretariat@ectp-ceu.eu>
Data 2023-05-25 11:05

Dear All,

Due to the experience of ECTP-CEU in Spatial Planning and Urban Development, we are contacting you in the context of the [Horizon 2030 project 'BioValue'](#). This project aims to leverage transformative change in spatial policymaking, planning practices and infrastructure development to upscale opportunities for valuing biodiversity in support of the EU's strategic actions.

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